

19/19
20
16
10

MINAB

K 143, 144, 145, 146.

22/22
26/26
28

~~1200~~ to KUNARDOM
~~300~~ 1000 300
300 300 400 200 500

Kung car.

Kun 1. boxes.

27

6.5 m	5
7	7
8.5	1
9	4
11	1

min. 9. 3+26
2+22
1+25

10/ 2+19
1+20
1+16
1+10

15 ✓

13 1
15 1

17 4
19 5

3 San Suts
no legs

#41

500 miles cards
food.